

Investigation of structural and magnetic properties of RBaFeMnO₆ (R = Nd, Sm) double perovskites

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Abstract

The polycrystalline RBaFeMnO₆ (R=Nd and Sm) double perovskites have been synthesized using nitrate-glycine auto-combustion synthesis method followed by single step calcination process [1]. The room temperature powder X-ray diffraction patterns reveal that synthesized samples crystallize into an ideal cubic perovskite crystal structure with space group Pm-3m. The structural parameters have been refined by Rietveld analysis method [2] using FullProf Suite software [3]. The value of lattice constant “a” decreases from a=3.894Å for NBFMO to a=3.889Å for SBFMO due to smaller ionic radius of Sm (0.958Å) than Nd (0.983Å) [4]. The temperature dependent magnetization M(T) curves reveal that these samples undergo paramagnetic to antiferromagnetic phase transition at Neel temperature T_N. The field dependence of magnetization M(H) measurement shows coexistence of ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic fractions at low temperature (5K). The UV-Vis spectroscopy measurement reveals high energy band gap between conduction band and valence band of the order of E_g~6eV.

“Keywords: X-Ray Diffraction; Auto-Combustion Method; Rietveld Refinement; FullProf Suite; Energy Band Gap.”

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